

Vanadium(V) initiated graft co-polymerization of vinyl monomers onto poly(vinyl alcohol)

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Abstract : The graft co-polymerization of vinyl monomers onto poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) by ammonium vanadate (AV) was studied as a function of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{AV}$ mole ratio, PVA/monomer weight ratio, sulfuric acid concentration, and reaction time and temperature. The presence of hydrogen peroxide at 2 N H_2SO_4 improves the grafting efficiency of vanadium(V). The optimum time and temperature of the grafting reaction was found to be 3.5 h and 55 °C respectively for the most reactive vinyl monomer studied. FT-IR spectroscopy was used for the confirmation of grafting. The thermal stability of the grafted polymer was evaluated. A generalized reaction scheme has been suggested to elucidate the role of vanadium(V) and hydrogen peroxide.

Keywords : Grafting, co-polymerization, pentavalent vanadium, FTIR, TGA, DSC.

Introduction

Graft modified polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)¹ possesses great potential in several industrial fields, such as temperature and pH sensitive hydrogels², soft tissue replacement³, water ethanol mixture separation membrane⁴, heavy metal ion separation membrane⁵, super adsorbent polymers⁶, controlled release of biologically active compounds⁷ and polymeric catalyst membranes⁸. Most of the graft polymerization of vinyl monomers onto PVA has been conducted in aqueous medium and they are initiated mainly by ceric ions^{9,10} along with few reports of cupric^{11,12}, ferric^{13,14} and nickel(IV)^{15,16} initiators. The serious drawback of ceric(IV) ion initiation is the production of homopolymer along with grafted polymer. Many research workers are trying to replace ceric ion by other efficient initiators such as pentavalent vanadium to reduce the homopolymerization. Vanadium(V) initiated graft co-polymerization of methyl methacrylate onto wool fibers¹⁷ and cotton cellulose¹⁸ were reported earlier. The co-initiators such as thiourea¹⁷, cyclohexanone¹⁹, etc. were used along with vanadium(V) to improve its efficiency. These co-initiators act as reducing agent to produce free radicals. These free radicals produce graft co-polymers along with undesirable homopolymers. Therefore an attempt has been made to reduce the homopolymerization and increase the grafting efficiency by using hydrogen peroxide (oxidizing agent) as co-initiator. No work has been done so far on the

grafting of PVA using vanadium(V) and hydrogen peroxide. In acid medium (pH < 2), vanadium(V) is reduced to vanadium(IV) through single electron transfer process^{20,21} with a redox potential : $\text{V}^{\text{V}}\text{O}_2^+ + 2\text{H}^+ + e = \text{V}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $E^\circ = 1.01$ V. The $\text{VO}_2^+/\text{VO}^{2+}$ system is capable of producing free radical at the backbone polymer where grafting starts¹⁸⁻²².

With this background, we have recently designed an initiator system based on ammonium vanadate (AV) and hydrogen peroxide (HP) for grafting PVA in aqueous medium. To the extent we searched the relevant literature, reports involving vanadium(V) initiation in presence of HP do not seem to exist. Some salient feature of the action of AV and HP are described in this paper.

Experimental

Materials :

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, Burgoyne Burbidges Company, India, viscosity average molecular weight = 16100, degree of hydrolysis = 98.4-99.0 mol%, viscosity = 26-31 cps) was used. Methyl methacrylate (MMA), ethyl methacrylate (EMA) and n-butyl methacrylate (BMA) (Merck, Germany) were purified¹⁴ before use. Ammonium vanadate (AV) (E. Merck, India) and hydrogen peroxide (30%, Qualigens, India) was used as received.

Table 1. Experimental results at various reaction conditions

Entry no.	HP/AV mole ratio	PVA/MMA weight ratio	H ₂ SO ₄ (M)	Time (h)	Temp. (°C)	Color	GR	GE (%)	H (%)
1	0.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.18	19.1	-
2	1.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Brown	0.18	19.1	-
3	2.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.28	29.8	-
4	4.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.65	69.1	-
5	8.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Light blue	0.65	69.1	15.5
6	20.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Light blue	0.64	68.8	36.2
7	4.00	0.27	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.15	4.0	12.1
8	4.00	0.53	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.24	13.2	7.1
9	4.00	1.60	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.52	83.0	-
10	4.00	2.12	0.1	3.5	55	Blue	0.38	80.8	-
11	4.00	1.06	1.0	3.5	55	Blue	-	-	-
12	4.00	1.06	1.5	3.5	55	Blue	-	-	-
13	4.00	1.06	4.0	3.5	55	Blue	0.31	17.6	-
14	4.00	1.06	2	3.5	55	Blue	0.48	51.1	-
15	4.00	1.06	2	1	55	Blue	0.19	20.14	-
16	4.00	1.06	2	2.0	55	Blue	0.41	43.46	-
17	4.00	1.06	2	3.0	55	Blue	0.50	53.00	-
18	4.00	1.06	2	4.0	55	Blue	0.60	69.96	-
19	4.00	1.06	2	3.5	25	Blue	0.25	26.50	-
20	4.00	1.06	2	3.5	50	Blue	0.45	47.7	-
21	4.00	1.06	2	3.5	60	Blue	0.60	63.6	-
22	4.00	1.06	2	3.5	70	Blue	0.55	58.3	-
23 ^a	4.00	0.00	2	3.5	55	Blue	-	-	14.3

Total volume of the reaction mixture = 100 ml, PVA (Poly Vinyl Alcohol) = 1 g, AV (Ammonium Vanadate) = 8.55×10^{-4} mole (0.1 g), HP (Hydrogen Peroxide) : variable, MMA (Methyl Metha Acrylate) : variable.

GR (Grafting Ratio) = (Wt. of PMMA grafted)/(Wt. of PVA), GE (Grafting Efficiency) = 100 (Wt. of PMMA grafted)/(Wt. of MMA), H (Homopolymerization) = 100 (Wt. of PMMA)/(Wt. of MMA).

^aThe system contains 3.7 g MMA without PVA.

Graft co-polymerization :

Graft co-polymerization was carried out following the procedure as described earlier^{23,24}. A definite amount of PVA (1 g) was stirred with a requisite quantity of vinyl monomers (0.94 g) for 15 min before graft polymerization was started. Total volume of the mixture was made to 100 ml by adding distilled water and AV (0.1 g) was then added to the reaction mixture (compositions of the mixtures are given in the Table 1). Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained throughout the reaction period. The solution was stirred magnetically and 1 : 4 H₂SO₄ (acid : water, by volume) was added dropwise. Polymerization was carried out at 55 °C under the acidity of 0.5 N H₂SO₄ both in presence and absence of hydrogen peroxide. The precipitated polymer was filtered off and washed repeatedly with dilute H₂SO₄.

The products were first extracted with water in Soxhlet apparatus for 72 h to free all the unreacted PVA and then with acetone for 72 h to remove the PMMA homopolymers. The colorless product dried under vacuum at 100 °C for more than 72 h to a constant weight. Isolated homopolymer from acetone was dried and weighed.

Characterization :

Grafting ratio (GR), grafting efficiency (GE), and percentage of homopolymerization (H) and grafting (G) were calculated using the following equations as described elsewhere^{23,24}.

GR = Weight of the polymer grafted/weight of PVA; GE (%) = (Weight of the polymer grafted/weight of the monomer used) × 100; H (%) = (Weight of the homopolymer isolated/weight of monomer used) × 100; G (%) = GR × 100.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the samples were recorded on a Shimadzu (Model No. 84005) FTIR system in the range of 450 to 4000 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets. Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted using a Stanton Redcraft thermal analyzer (STA-780) in air at a rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The pH of the reaction medium was measured by a pH meter (Elico, India, Model LI 120).

Results and discussion

Effect of vinyl monomers :

Graft co-polymerization was studied with different vinyl monomers such as methyl methacrylate (MMA), ethyl methacrylate (EMA) and n-butyl methacrylate (BMA). The order of grafting efficiency was found as $\text{MMA} > \text{EMA} > \text{BMA}$ (Fig. 1). The highest reactivity of MMA is probably due to the least bulkiness of the corresponding tertiary free radicals.

Fig. 1. Bar diagram of grafting efficiency (GE) of different vinyl monomers.

Evidence of grafting :

The presence of PMMA on the PVA molecules was verified by the FTIR spectra of PVA and grafted PVA (Fig. 2). Both the spectra of PVA and grafted PVA show a characteristic broad absorption band around 3480 to 2910 cm^{-1} . This is attributed to the O-H bond stretching vibration of PVA^{27,28}. The spectrum of the grafted PVA exhibits a strong absorption band at 1730 cm^{-1} , which is absent in the spectrum of PVA. The peak near 1730 cm^{-1} could be associated with the C=O stretching vibration of an ester group from MMA^{27,28}. The appearance of a new peak at 1730 cm^{-1} in the resulted copolymer provides strong evidence of grafting. Similarly grafting of EMA and BMA onto PVA was confirmed by FTIR spectral analysis.

PVA is soluble in water but insoluble in acetone. While PMMA, PEMA and PBMA are insoluble in water but soluble in acetone. PVA, graft co-polymerized with vinyl monomer (grafting > 18%) is insoluble in both water and acetone. The insolubility in the pure solvents is attributable to the change in polymer composition. At low grafting level (grafting \leq 18%), the PVA copolymer is fairly soluble in hot water but insoluble in cold water. The uncross-linked grafting (eq. 3, reaction scheme) is probably responsible for solubility in hot water, but not in cold one.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) PVA and (b) grafted PVA.

Fig. 3(a). Simultaneous TG-DSC curves of PVA.

Fig. 3(b). Simultaneous TG-DSC curves of grafted PVA.

Thermal analysis :

Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) are the TGA and DSC traces of PVA and PMMA-g-PVA respectively. Integral procedure decomposition temperature (IPDT)²⁹ was calculated from TGA curve as follows :

$$IPDT (°C) = A.K. (T_f - T_i) + T_i;$$

$$A = (S_1 + S_2)/(S_1 + S_2 + S_3); K = (S_1 + S_2)/S_1$$

T_i is the initial temperature (25 °C in this work) and T_f is the final experimental temperature (350 °C for PVA and 450 °C for grafted PVA) for TGA. S_1 , S_2 and S_3 denote the area specified in the TGA curve (not DSC curve). The IPDT values are found to be 315 and 403 °C for PVA and grafted PVA respectively. Higher IPDT value indicates the better thermal stability of the grafted polymer.

The activation energy, E_a , for the thermal decomposition of the polymers is obtained from thermo-gram by the integral method³⁰ according to the following equation :

$$\ln\{\ln(1 - \alpha)^{-1}\} = E_a\theta/RT_{\max}^2$$

where $\theta = T - T_{\max}$, α is the decomposition ratio (weight loss/initial weight) and R denotes the universal gas constant. T and T_{\max} denote decomposition temperature and temperature of maximum rate of weight loss respectively ($T_{\max} = 275$ °C for PVA and 390 °C for grafted PVA). The maximum rate of weight loss was found from the rate of weight loss versus temperature plot (plot is not shown here). The activation energy E_a is calculated from the tangent of the straight line corresponding to the $\ln\{\ln(1 - \alpha)^{-1}\}$ versus θ as shown in

Fig. 4(a). The $\ln\{\ln(1 - \alpha)^{-1}\}$ versus θ curve for PVA.

Fig. 4(b). The $\ln\{\ln(1 - \alpha)^{-1}\}$ versus θ curve for grafted PVA.

Figs. 4(a) (for PVA) and 4(b) (for grafted PVA). E_a for PVA and grafted PVA are found 143.8 and 228.0 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The higher activation energy for the thermal decomposition of grafted PVA reflects its better thermal stability.

DSC curve of PVA [Fig. 3(a)] clearly shows a T_m (crystalline melting point) of the used PVA at 220 °C. The endothermic peaks at 100 and 275 °C are probably due to evolution of water and thermal decomposition of PVA respectively. DSC curve of grafted PVA [Fig. 3(b)] shows two peaks at 116 and 390 °C, which may be attributed to the evolution of water and thermal decomposition of grafted polymer respectively. Higher decomposition temperature of grafted PVA indicates its better thermal stability than ungrafted one.

Features of polymerization in absence hydrogen peroxide :

The addition of AV to an aqueous solution (pH > 7) of vinyl monomers and PVA does not lead to polymer formation and any change in color of the solution. However, the dropwise addition of 1 : 4 H₂SO₄, gradually changes the color of the solution from colorless to brown at a pH around 5. With the continued addition of acid, the solution gradually becomes pale yellow at a pH around 3. Further addition of sulfuric acid (pH < 2), makes the solution blue. The color change of the solution with the variation of pH of the aqueous medium may be explained with the help of following transformation as reported in the literature^{20,21}.

The PVA acts as a mild reducing agent to reduce vanadyl ion, $[V^{VO_2}]^+$ to oxovanadium ion, $[V^{IVO}]^{2+}$ at pH around 2. The oxidation of PVA by vanadium(v) results in graft polymerization as follows :

Termination by disproportionation :

Termination by coupling :

Searching of optimum hydrogen peroxide (HP)/ammonium vanadate (AV) mole ratio :

The presence of hydrogen peroxide changes the system remarkably (Table 1, Entry No. 1–6). It is observed that the percentage of grafting and grafting efficiency (GE) increase with the increase of HP/AV mole ratio up to 4 and then levels off with further increase of mole ratio. The blue (Entry 1) and brown (Entry 2) color of the reaction medium is due to the formation of oxovanadium(V) [VO^{2+}] and peroxovanadium(V) [$\text{V}(\text{-O-O})$] respectively^{20,21}. The optimum HP/AV mole ratio for the production of graft co-polymer was observed at 4. The H_2O_2 is stronger oxidizing agent than VO_2^+ in acid medium^{20,21}. Thus it is highly probable that H_2O_2 oxidizes the VO^{2+} to VO_2^+ , which in turn intensify the grafting reactions (eqs. 1–4). The excess H_2O_2 (Entry 5 and 6) leads to the production of homopolymer without enhancing the graft co-polymerization level. In these conditions H_2O_2 may produce HO radicals, which are responsible for the production of homopolymer. The optimum HP/AV mole ratio for other monomers EMA and BMA were found at 4.5 and 4.8 respectively.

Controlling of grafting by PVA/monomer weight ratio :

The effect of increasing weight ratio of PVA/MMA on grafting is shown in Table 1 (Entry No. 4 and 7–10). The percentage of grafting and grafting efficiency were increased with the increase of weight ratio up to 1.06. Further increase of PVA, made the system inefficient with respect to grafting. From the experimental results it is evident that amount of PVA plays an important role in controlling the extent of grafting, grafting efficiency and percentage of homo-polymerization. Availability of greater amount of monomers enhances the formation of homopolymer (Entry No. 7 and 8). MMA homopolymerizes to a low extent (14.3%) in absence of PVA (Entry No. 23). The optimum PVA/monomer weight ratio were found to be 1.06, 1.09 and 1.12 for MMA, EMA and BMA respectively.

Finding of optimum sulfuric acid concentration :

The effect of sulfuric acid concentration on polymerization at a particular level of other reagents is given in Table 1 (Entry No. 4 and 10–14). The reaction medium was turned red brown at 1.5 N, due to the production of peroxovanadium(V) complex. The 2 N H_2SO_4 made the system most productive. Vanadyl ion, VO_2^+ ; probably produced at 2 N acid condition. The produced ion leads to graft polymerization through series of reactions (1–4). Further increase of acid beyond 4 N deactivates the

system, probably due to hydrolysis of the polymer produced. The most effective acid concentration was 2 N H_2SO_4 for all the vinyl monomers used.

Effect of time :

The effect of time on grafting yield in case of MMA is shown in Table 1 (Entry No. 4 and 15–18). The grafting ratio (GR) increases with the increase of time and reaches its maximum at 3.5 h. After 3.5 h, the GR increases marginally with time. Thus the optimum reaction period under specified reaction conditions was found 3.5 h. The polymerization is a chain reaction with initiation, propagation and termination steps. So, with time grafted polymer formation increases because new radical centers are generated on PVA. PMMA grows from PVA radical and then terminates (eqs. 1–4, reaction scheme). New chains start from PVA and then the process repeats. The optimum reaction times were observed 3.75 h and 4.2 h for EMA and BMA respectively. The less reactive monomer needs higher reaction time.

Effect of temperature :

The polymerization reaction was carried out within the temperature range from 30 to 70 °C and the results are exhibited in Table 1 (Entry No. 4 and 19–22). The GR increases with the increase of temperature up to 55 °C and then it decreases with further increase of temperature. There is an overall activation energy of graft co-polymerization. The rate of co-polymerization therefore increases with increase of temperature. The evaporation of monomer may substantiate the decrease in grafting level after 55 °C. The suitable temperature of grafting for EMA and BMA were 59 and 64 °C respectively. The less reactivity of EMA and BMA is probably responsible for their higher reaction temperature.

Conclusions :

The order of grafting efficiency in presence of pentavalent vanadium was found as MMA > EMA > BMA. The graft polymerization of vinyl monomers onto PVA by ammonium vanadate and hydrogen peroxide in aqueous medium can be controlled by varying HP/AV mole ratio, PVA/monomer weight ratio and reaction temperature and time. The grafting becomes optimum at HP/AV mole ratio of 4, PVA/MMA weight ratio of 1.06, 2 N H_2SO_4 , 55 °C, and 3.5 h for MMA (the most reactive vinyl monomers studied). FTIR spectroscopy confirms the vinyl grafting of PVA. The thermal properties of the grafted PVA are much improved

due to grafting. The role of vanadium(V) is to produce PVA macro radical where grafting starts. Hydrogen peroxide increases the grafting level significantly.

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